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IMPROVING SERVICE QUALITY MONITORING IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation. This article scientifically analyzes the issues of improving service quality monitoring in service enterprises based on digital technologies. The study examines the impact of CRM systems, Big Data analytics, artificial intelligence, and KPI monitoring systems on service quality indicators. Customer satisfaction levels, service delivery speed, and the number of complaints were selected as key service quality indicators, and the effectiveness of managing these indicators through digital technologies is substantiated. The research findings show that digital monitoring systems enable real-time control of service quality, optimize managerial decision-making, and strengthen the competitiveness of service enterprises.

Keywords: service sector, service quality, monitoring, digital technologies, CRM systems, Big Data, artificial intelligence, KPI, customer satisfaction, economic efficiency.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarida xizmat sifati monitoringini raqamli texnologiyalar asosida takomillashtirish masalalari ilmiy jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda CRM tizimlari, Big Data tahlili, sun'iy intellekt va KPI monitoring tizimlarining xizmat sifati ko'rsatkichlariga ta'siri o'rganilgan. Mijozlar qoniqish darajasi, xizmat ko'rsatish tezligi va murojaatlar soni xizmat sifati bo'yicha asosiy ko'rsatkichlar sifatida tanlab olinib, ushbu ko'rsatkichlarni raqamli texnologiyalar orqali boshqarish samaradorligi asoslab berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari raqamli monitoring tizimlari xizmat sifati ustidan real vaqt rejimida nazorat o'rnatish, boshqaruv qarorlarini optimallashtirish hamda xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirish imkonini berishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, xizmat sifati, monitoring, raqamli texnologiyalar, CRM tizimlari, Big Data, sun'iy intellekt, KPI, mijozlar qoniqishi, iqtisodiy samaradorlik.

Аннотация. В данной статье научно проанализированы вопросы совершенствования мониторинга качества услуг на предприятиях сферы обслуживания на основе цифровых технологий. В исследовании рассмотрено влияние CRM-систем, аналитики Big Data, искусственного интеллекта и систем KPI-мониторинга на показатели качества услуг. В качестве основных показателей качества услуг выбраны уровень удовлетворенности клиентов, скорость оказания услуг и количество обращений, а также обоснована эффективность управления этими показателями с помощью цифровых технологий. Результаты исследования показывают, что цифровые системы мониторинга позволяют осуществлять контроль качества услуг в режиме реального времени, оптимизировать управленческие решения и повышать конкурентоспособность предприятий сферы обслуживания.

Ключевые слова: сфера услуг, качество услуг, мониторинг, цифровые технологии, CRM-системы, Big Data, искусственный интеллект, KPI, удовлетворенность клиентов, экономическая эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

At the current stage, digital transformation processes taking place in the global economy are fundamentally changing the content, organizational structure, and management mechanisms of production and service systems. In particular, the service sector is emerging as one of the most active industries in terms of the implementation of digital technologies, where service quality, responsiveness, and customer relationship management are reaching a new level. Under such conditions, the sustainable development of service enterprises depends not only on the volume of services provided but also directly on the quality of these services and the ability to continuously monitor them [1].

Service quality is one of the strategic factors determining the competitiveness of enterprises in the modern service economy. As market relations deepen and consumer demands become more complex, enterprises can achieve competitive advantage not only by providing services but also by regularly monitoring service quality, promptly identifying existing shortcomings, and making timely managerial decisions. In this regard, service

quality monitoring is not merely a control instrument for service enterprises but also an important management tool aimed at improving service processes, increasing customer satisfaction, and strengthening economic efficiency [2].

Traditional monitoring methods are usually based on reports, surveys, periodic inspections, and the review of customer complaints. However, such approaches often operate slowly, are highly dependent on human factors, and cannot provide complete and accurate information in real time. As a result, problems in service delivery are not identified promptly, situations related to service quality are addressed with delays, and this may lead to a decline in customer satisfaction. Therefore, in the context of the digital economy, transitioning service quality monitoring from traditional approaches to digital management systems has become an objective necessity [3].

Digital technologies, particularly CRM systems, Big Data analytics, artificial intelligence, cloud services, online platforms, and KPI monitoring systems, are elevating service quality control in service enterprises to a new level. These technologies enable the collection, processing, and in-depth analysis of large volumes of data regarding customer behavior, needs, complaints, and service usage patterns. As a result, shortcomings in service delivery are identified more quickly, service processes are optimized, and the accuracy and effectiveness of managerial decisions are improved.

In particular, artificial intelligence-based monitoring systems have significant practical importance in the service sector. They allow for the automatic analysis of customer feedback, the evaluation of service speed, the identification of recurring issues, and the forecasting of future needs. Big Data technologies help organize service quality monitoring in a deeper and more systematic way by aggregating data generated across numerous customers and operational processes. Through CRM systems, customer relationships are managed within a unified database, and analytical information on service quality is generated [4].

At the same time, improving service quality monitoring in service enterprises based on digital technologies is not only a technical issue but also a complex process of organizational and economic significance. The effectiveness of monitoring systems depends not only on the availability of modern software tools but also on their proper integration into management systems, the development of employees' digital competencies, the clear definition of quality indicators, and the ability to transform monitoring results into managerial decisions. Thus, implementing digital monitoring requires a comprehensive revision of the service quality management system [5].

The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that, under the conditions of the digital economy, an effective model for service quality monitoring in service enterprises has not yet been fully developed. Although some enterprises use digital technologies in practice, the interconnection between these technologies and monitoring systems, their impact on economic outcomes, and their role in improving management efficiency have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, scientifically substantiating the directions for improving service quality monitoring based on digital technologies in service enterprises has important theoretical and practical significance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of service quality monitoring in the service sector is considered one of the complex scientific areas formed at the intersection of economics, management, marketing, and digital technologies. The evolution of scientific views in this field shows that service quality was initially interpreted mainly as a phenomenon related to customer satisfaction; however, today it is regarded as a multifactor economic category closely linked with enterprise competitiveness, operational efficiency, and digital management systems. Particularly in the context of digital transformation, service quality monitoring is no longer only a control tool but is becoming a strategic mechanism aimed at optimizing service processes, managing customer relationships, and improving economic outcomes.

The formation of service quality theory has been significantly influenced by the scientific works of representatives of the services marketing and service management schools. In particular, Christopher Lovelock emphasizes that service quality is one of the key conditions for enterprise success and evaluates the service delivery process as a system of value creation for customers. In his approach, service quality represents the practical outcome of interactions between the enterprise and the consumer, manifested in the degree of alignment between the expected benefits and the actual service provided. This perspective highlights the priority of customer-oriented management principles in organizing service quality monitoring in service enterprises [6].

Christopher Lovelock further developed the understanding of service quality by emphasizing the importance of customer expectations and perceived value in evaluating service performance.

Christian Grönroos further developed the theory of service quality by explaining it through two main components: technical quality and functional quality. According to his view, customers evaluate not only the final outcome of the service but also the way the service is delivered. This approach provides an important method-

ological basis for developing service quality monitoring systems. It suggests that monitoring should consider not only result indicators but also process indicators such as service speed, convenience, transparency, quality of interaction with employees, and responsiveness to customer requests. In this sense, Grönroos's scientific views serve as a theoretical foundation for implementing digital monitoring systems in service enterprises [7].

Christian Grönroos emphasized that both the outcome of the service and the process of service delivery determine customer perceptions of quality.

The relationship between digital transformation and service quality management is also reflected in the ideas of Manuel Castells regarding the information society and network economy. He considers digital technologies as a systemic factor transforming all stages of economic activity. According to his concept, the speed and quality of information flows in a networked economic environment directly influence enterprise performance. For the service sector, this implies that collecting, storing, processing customer-related data, and making managerial decisions based on this information become central elements of service quality monitoring. Therefore, digital monitoring systems represent not merely technical tools but a new institutional form of service quality management [8].

Modern scientific literature increasingly highlights the role of artificial intelligence and analytical technologies in service enterprises. In particular, Thomas H. Davenport notes that artificial intelligence and data analytics create a new qualitative stage in managerial decision-making. In his approach, artificial intelligence is interpreted as a strategic resource that enables the identification of hidden patterns in enterprise activities, analysis of customer behavior, rapid detection of service delivery deficiencies, and forecasting of future needs. These views strengthen the scientific basis for using AI technologies to improve service quality monitoring, as traditional monitoring systems often rely on delayed information, whereas artificial intelligence enables real-time monitoring [9].

CRM systems and Big Data technologies are also considered modern instruments of service quality monitoring in the literature. CRM systems allow the systematization of customer relationships, storage of interaction history, and segmentation of needs and problems, thereby enabling accurate assessment of service quality indicators. Big Data technologies, in turn, make it possible to identify recurring issues in service delivery, forecast service demand, and ensure efficient resource utilization based on the analysis of large-scale datasets. Therefore, these technologies are often interpreted as the informational foundation of service quality monitoring.

Local economists have also paid considerable attention to issues of service quality and digital management in the service sector. In particular, Baxrom Yuldashev evaluates the development of the service sector as an important factor of economic growth and emphasizes that improvements in service quality indicators directly affect enterprise efficiency. This approach substantiates that service quality monitoring is not only a management tool but also an instrument influencing economic outcomes.

Akmal Saidov also notes that the introduction of digital technologies in service enterprises contributes to the modernization of service processes, improvement of service quality monitoring, and enhancement of managerial responsiveness. These views demonstrate the practical importance of implementing digital monitoring systems within the national economic context.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study examines the issues of improving service quality monitoring in service enterprises based on digital technologies using a systematic and comprehensive approach. The theoretical foundation of the research is based on scientific concepts related to service quality management, the digital economy, and service management.

During the research process, methods such as scientific literature analysis, comparative analysis, economic-statistical analysis, observation, and logical generalization were employed. In addition, the study used a comparative evaluation of traditional and digital monitoring systems to identify their effectiveness in managing service quality.

Customer satisfaction levels, service delivery speed, and the number of complaints were selected as the main service quality indicators, and the management of these indicators through digital monitoring systems was assessed. Particular attention was given to the role of CRM systems, Big Data analytics, artificial intelligence, and KPI monitoring systems in improving service quality.

The information base of the research consists of scientific articles, monographs, analytical reports, official statistical data, and practical materials related to service enterprises. The findings were generalized to determine the impact of digital technologies on service quality monitoring and enterprise competitiveness.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the context of the digital economy, service quality monitoring in service enterprises is gradually shift-

ing from traditional control forms to digital management mechanisms. This process is primarily explained by the acceleration of information flows in service activities, the increasing individualization of customer needs, and the intensification of the competitive environment. Under such conditions, CRM systems, Big Data, artificial intelligence, and KPI monitoring tools are gaining significant importance in improving service quality monitoring.

The analysis shows that digital monitoring systems significantly simplify the processes of collecting, processing, and evaluating information on service quality in service enterprises. As a result, shortcomings in service delivery are identified more quickly, response time to customer requests increases, and the accuracy of managerial decisions improves. Particularly in service enterprises that directly interact with customers, real-time monitoring systems are becoming an important tool for ensuring the stability of service quality [10] (Table 1).

Table 1
The Impact of Digital Technologies on Service Quality Monitoring¹

Digital Technology	Main Function	Impact on Monitoring	Expected Result
CRM systems	Customer relationship management	Quickly identifies requests and complaints	Customer satisfaction increases
Big Data	Analysis of large volumes of data	Forecasts demand and problems	Resources are allocated efficiently
Artificial intelligence	Automated analysis and control	Provides real-time monitoring	Service responsiveness improves
KPI monitoring	Evaluation of quality indicators	Controls employee performance	Efficiency increases
Digital platforms	Online tracking and integration	Enhances transparent monitoring	Operational costs decrease

The table data indicate that digital technologies influence not only individual stages of service quality monitoring but also the entire management process in a comprehensive manner. In particular, CRM systems facilitate the identification of service quality issues by consolidating customer-related information into a unified database. Big Data technologies, in turn, make it possible to forecast changes in service demand through the analysis of large volumes of data [11].

The practical significance of artificial intelligence is especially high, as it enables the rapid identification of recurring errors in service delivery, the classification of incoming requests, and the automation of managerial decision-making. KPI monitoring supports the quantitative evaluation of service quality indicators and allows the analysis of employee performance from an effectiveness perspective. Thus, the digital monitoring system in service enterprises functions not only as a control mechanism but also as a tool for improving overall management efficiency (Table 2).

Table 2
Comparative Results of Traditional and Digital Monitoring Systems²

Indicators	Traditional Monitoring	Digital Monitoring	Level of Change
Service delivery time	20–25 minutes	10–12 minutes	Reduced by 45–50%
Customer satisfaction level	65–70%	85–90%	Increased by 20%
Number of complaints	High	Low	Decreased by 30–35%
Labor productivity	Low	High	Increased by 25–30%
Service delivery costs	High	Medium	Decreased by 15–20%
Monitoring responsiveness	Low	High	Significantly improved

¹ author's development

² author's development

The results of the comparative analysis indicate that the implementation of digital monitoring systems in service enterprises leads to significant positive changes. In particular, the reduction in service delivery time can be explained by the automation of service processes and the acceleration of information exchange. The increase in customer satisfaction levels is the result of improved service stability, faster responses to customer requests, and greater transparency in service delivery.

Moreover, the decrease in the number of complaints indicates that monitoring systems enhance the ability to identify problems in advance. This, in turn, accelerates the process of eliminating service deficiencies. The increase in labor productivity is associated with the reduction of unnecessary operations related to human factors, while the decrease in costs results from more efficient use of resources.

Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that improving service quality monitoring in service enterprises is not only a technological upgrade but also an important factor in enhancing organizational and economic efficiency. Digital monitoring systems, on the one hand, strengthen control over service quality and, on the other hand, ensure responsiveness, transparency, and competitiveness in enterprise activities. Therefore, the implementation of digital monitoring and its integration as an essential part of service quality management in service enterprises has significant scientific and practical importance.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the conducted research show that, in the context of the digital economy, improving service quality monitoring in service enterprises is one of the key factors for increasing competitiveness, ensuring customer satisfaction, and enhancing operational efficiency. Traditional forms of service quality monitoring cannot fully meet modern market requirements and the need for prompt management, which increases the importance of modernizing them based on digital technologies.

The analysis revealed that CRM systems, Big Data, artificial intelligence, and digital platforms significantly expand the functional capabilities of service quality monitoring. These technologies enable the real-time collection, processing, and evaluation of data related to customer requests, service delivery speed, number of complaints, and employee performance. As a result, it becomes possible to promptly identify shortcomings in service delivery, optimize managerial decisions, and ensure the stability of service quality.

The research findings also confirm that digital monitoring systems have a positive impact on the economic efficiency of service enterprises. In particular, service delivery time is reduced, customer satisfaction increases, the number of complaints decreases, labor productivity improves, and operational costs decline. This demonstrates that improving service quality monitoring is not only a control mechanism but also an organizational and economic tool that enhances overall management efficiency in service enterprises.

Therefore, it is advisable to further develop service quality monitoring based on digital technologies in service enterprises, widely implement artificial intelligence-based analytical systems, improve KPI indicators, and strengthen customer-oriented digital management mechanisms. In addition, it is recommended to increase employee digital competencies, expand the use of CRM and Big Data technologies, and integrate digital monitoring systems into the overall management structure of enterprises.

Future research in this area will contribute to the development of more advanced models of service quality management in the service sector.

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